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KOHONEN'S SELF-ORGANIZING MAPS (SOM) AS A LEADING METHOD FOR FORECASTING AND MODELING SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

Abstract. Kohonen's Self-Organizing Maps (SOM) have gained immense popularity across diverse disciplines, encompassing finance, economics, and regional development studies. These maps offer a powerful tool for unraveling intricate phenomena and tackling prevalent challenges in these domains.

Key findings. Within the financial industry, SOM has been harnessed for multiple purposes. It facilitates the identification and prevention of fraud in the leasing sector, enhances market segmentation by clustering retail banking customers, and uncovers hidden financial patterns embedded in stock price charts. Additionally, SOM enables the visualization of complex financial performance data, aiding analysts in deciphering historical trends and making informed decisions.

In addition to the financial applications, numerous researchers have explored the potential of SOM in various fields. For instance, researchers Mirjana PEJIĆ BACH, Nikola VLAHOVIĆ, And Jasmina PIVAR [1] have utilized SOM to detect and prevent fraud in the leasing sector. Their study showcases the effectiveness of SOM in enhancing security measures and safeguarding financial transactions.

Tibor Kovács, Andrea Ko, and Asefeh Asemi [2] have employed SOM to cluster retail banking customers, enabling targeted marketing strategies and personalized customer experiences. By harnessing the capabilities of SOM, they have enhanced customer segmentation techniques and improved the efficiency of the banking sector.

Hongxing He and Shu-Heng Chen [3] have delved into the realm of financial patterns by utilizing SOM to analyze stock price charts. Their research highlights the potential of SOM in uncovering hidden trends and patterns within financial

markets, contributing to more accurate predictions and informed investment decisions.

Manchuna Shanmuganathan [4] has exclusively focused on financial performance visualization, utilizing SOM to examine the financial history of a Canadian bank. By visualizing financial data through SOM, she has provided valuable insights into the bank's performance, enabling stakeholders to make strategic decisions and assess financial stability effectively.

Additionally, researchers such as Man Ha [5] and Magnus Nordlinder [6] have explored the applications of SOM in specific country contexts. Man Ha has utilized SOM for analyzing the Bank of Vietnam's data, while Magnus Nordlinder has applied SOM to examine financial data related to Sweden. These studies demonstrate the versatility of SOM in capturing country-specific dynamics and informing economic policies tailored to specific contexts.

Furthermore, Guido Deboeck [7] has compiled a comprehensive overview of SOM applications in the financial sector, highlighting its potential across various domains, including risk analysis, portfolio management, and financial forecasting. His work provides a comprehensive resource for researchers and practitioners interested in leveraging SOM for financial applications.

In geographic sciences, Geo-SOM, a specialized variant of SOM, has opened up new possibilities for analyzing regional development and uncovering underlying spatial structures. This breakthrough contributes significantly to the advancement of geosciences, facilitating a comprehensive understanding of homogeneous regions and their intricate relationships.

Moreover, SOM plays a pivotal role in macroeconomic studies. It empowers researchers to predict and assess financial crises, compare countries by clustering them based on key economic indicators, and identify macroeconomic disequilibrium among European nations. These explorations shed light on complex economic dynamics, enabling policymakers to formulate targeted strategies for sustainable growth and regional cooperation.

The European Central Bank [8] recognizes the value of SOM in studying financial stability and discerning interconnections within the intricate web of the financial system. SOM's ability to unveil similarities and dependencies provides policymakers with a robust framework for designing effective regulatory measures, ensuring a resilient and well-functioning financial ecosystem.

These diverse studies underscore the broad spectrum of research conducted using SOM. By leveraging the unique capabilities of SOM, researchers across different disciplines continue to explore its potential in addressing complex challenges and uncovering insights that drive innovation and informed decision-making.

In summary, the widespread adoption of Kohonen's Self-Organizing Maps across various domains underscores their versatility and efficacy in addressing multifaceted research questions and challenges.

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OPORTUNITATEA IMPLEMENTĂRII INTELIGENȚEI ARTIFICIALE PENTRU ÎMBUNĂTĂȚIREA PRODUCTIVITĂȚII COMPANIILOR DE ENERGIE TERMICĂ

Abstract. *În procesul de dezvoltare furibundă a societății și relațiilor interumane, apar noi relații pe alocuri imprevizibile care își pun amprenta pe viața zi de zi a oamenilor. Această situație este amplificată și de dezvoltarea rapidă a tehnologiilor dar și a componentelor „intelect” a acestor tehnologii care în cazul în care sunt utilizate corect pot contribui la eficientizarea, optimizarea unor procese importante, precum și la ridicarea productivității.*

Un rol deosebit, în acest proces îi revine tot mai des așa numitei „intelligenți artificiale” (în continuare IA), în ultimii ani, ea a devenit din ce în ce mai importantă în lumea afacerilor și industriilor. Oportunitățile oferite de această tehnologie sunt greu de subestimat, însă una dintre cele mai interesante și promițătoare este utilizarea ei pentru îmbunătățirea productivității, în special la întreprinderi, dar și în procesul de activitate a unei persoane, privită individual prin sporirea productivității activităților pe care le desfășoară.

Termeni cheie: management, inteligență artificială, productivitate, dezvoltare, avantaje, provocări

Annotation. *In the process of the booming development of society and interpersonal relations, new and sometimes unpredictable relationships are*